

ON STRICT PROOF OF “P VERSUS NP” THEOREM

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ABSTRACT

We give the strict proof of the inequivalence of the Computational Complexity Classes along with the previously obtained results which clearly give the outcome of the proof of division between P and NP classes which are unequal in general case, later on in this work we present the main discussion of the perspectives of the main outcome.

PROOFS AND ETC.

The theorem of “P versus NP” [1] states that, first, there are relations between idempotent Complexity Classes which weren’t defined in time [2] which led to diverse outcomes [3] stating the not tractable and readable proofs of the obvious question if P would equal NP.

The main perspectives led to our definition of the Functional Hypothesis [4] which led to the outcome of the existence of the feasible solution for NP-hard problem, which was obviously disproved in [5]. As it goes further, we are to define the parallel computation model which is weak before the algorithmic approaches of efficiently solving NP-hard problem, thus it follows that:

$$NP = N \cdot P.$$

From the above it follows that even finitary model of computation of either Turing or non-Turing machines is improper to define the solution which could be verified in polynomial time or even sought within the pre-defined models of computation.

Yes, of course, the outcome of $P = NP$ would lead to fantastic results like if the modern cryptosystems could be compromised in almost linear time – that’s not truth since even high-end computation model like parallel systems cannot solve the NP-hard problem in the visible amount of time, as it’s shown previously in [5].

As we have also shown in our prior works [6] determinately devoted to the resolution of “P versus NP” theorem proposed by Stephen Cook, we can convert the Non-deterministic Turing Machine (NDTM) to the equivalent Deterministic Finite Automaton (DFA), which correctly throughputs all the results of the output produced by NDTM during the operable simulation on the given input, same for either NDTM or DFA. This fact justifies the dramatic case or simply “error” which researchers permitted before by stating that from the fact, if $P = NP$, it follows that we can efficiently solve the NP-hard problems. Thus, if even according to our final proof P and NP are different and unequal as well as other classes according to the Parallel Computation Law (PCL) [4], it doesn’t mean that NP-hard problem cannot be solved efficiently as we can convert the Turing Machine and apply the law in a more different and elegant way by choosing the proper strategies for converting NDTM to DFA by Subset Construction as it was opposed due to Michael O. Rabin and Dana S. Scott and their seminal work [7], which was honored by the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) as Turing Award. The latter results were shown to solve even back-reference problem which is NP-hard strictly in polynomial time by applying pre-computation rule. Still, even if the problem leads to the estimated exponential or non-polynomial growth, the accuracy of algorithm gives the solution [8] which is almost as effective as the basement upon giving the 100% solution. According to our pre-dominant research even heuristics [9] can give almost poly-linear solution with a tight bound of accuracy whose speed is much lower than the speed of growing complexity of the problems like MAX-SAT or TSP.

The mathematical sense and the common understanding of the importance of the “P versus NP” question gives the rise to the operational relation between functions and their finitary properties [9]. These properties give the main proof of finitary nature of the geometrical sense of the point lying on the surface as well as the finite polynomial class belonging to the high-speed growing NP-class.

Here we give the proof by PCL as follows:

$$\lim_{\top}(N \rightarrow \infty) \llbracket NP/N = P, P = NP(\Rightarrow \top) 0 = 1(\Rightarrow \top) P \neq NP. \rrbracket$$

As it follows from [11] the axiomatization principle of P and NP as decidable and undecidable is also incorrect giving the partial proof of existence of the point on spherical surface which lies strictly on it within the multi-dimensional space.

Thus, even if we have shown that P and NP are unequal, there is still the set of problems which can be NP-hard and reduced to the proper computational class in the strictly linear and hierarchical order according to the relation between the complexities of these classes. The fact that if there is the set of problems which can be solved by a polynomial algorithm and in the same time belonging to the non-polynomial class is just a way of showing

that $P = NP$ [12], still as we can see this is a partial solution as there can be problems which belong to P and NP classes respectively due to the initial proof that P is a subset of NP .

The common mathematical axiomatization principle [13, 14] is a way of expressing the correct statement, however, due to the Cook's proofs, it follows that there are problems which lay strictly in NP -hard class and belong to NP as well to the minor P -class.

The TSP principle on integral circuits [15] is a way of solving the problem in full state space with the help of the candidate choosing algorithm which was well studied in Yen's algorithm [16].

The novel proof scheme by the statistical seed of probability was also presented [10], giving the underline of the existence of one-way hashing functions.

The genuine finding is due to Akram Louiz [17] about the cardinality of complexity classes which gives the indispensable proof of the difference of classes and the existence of the relation between them which is arbitrated by the PCL. Other researchers [18] tend to the mathematical sense of the theorem as there is no definition of the relation of Complexity Classes and the opposition of it to the infinity operator and, in common, the infinitary spaces or sets.

Conclusion

As we have shown the almost axiomatic proof of inequivalence of P and NP -classes, we have also given the full law along which the relation between Computational Complexity Classes can be devised. We have also proved that according to PCL the strict hierarchy along the relation of complexity classes exist. Thus, we have also shown that existence of polynomial solution for NP -hard problem is a partial case of proof of the equivalence of $P = NP$ due to the fact that the problem can lay in both classes as P is a subset of NP -class. The mathematical sense of the problem cannot be also omitted as the relation between classes according to their complexity gives the solution of the classes of congruence of the functions as well as the main theorem that point can belong to the sphere in any dimension.

Thus, we went through a long way of misunderstandings and mis proofs as well as the correct notation of the initial statement of the important theorem and stand-back from the long-time crisis in Computer Science as the proof of inequivalence of Complexity Classes doesn't mean that NP -hard problem cannot be solved efficiently in polynomial time, still it follows that we are to review all the pros and cons of the underlying theory and its evaluation through the paradigm of time and Mathematics.

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References

- [1] Cook, Stephen. "The P versus NP problem." Clay Mathematics Institute 2 (2000): 6.
- [2] Fortnow, Lance. "The status of the P versus NP problem." Communications of the ACM 52.9 (2009): 78-86.
- [3] Vega, Frank. "Sparse complete sets for coNP: Solution of the P versus NP problem." (2021).
- [4] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Functional hypothesis of complexity classes." Advanced technologies and computer science 3 (2021): 4-9.
- [5] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Inequivalence of Polynomial and Non-Polynomial Complexity Classes."
- [6] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Isomorphism of Turing Automata Output and Regular Languages."
- [7] Rabin, Michael O., and Dana Scott. "Finite automata and their decision problems." IBM journal of research and development 3.2 (1959): 114-125.
- [8] Prates, Marcelo, et al. "Learning to solve np-complete problems: A graph neural network for decision tsp." Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence. Vol. 33. No. 01. 2019.
- [9] Dorigo, Marco, Mauro Birattari, and Thomas Stutzle. "Ant colony optimization." IEEE computational intelligence magazine 1.4 (2006): 28-39.
- [10] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Artificial Intelligence for Complexity Theory." ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES AND COMPUTER SCIENCE 1.3 (2023): 27-31.
- [11] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Zermelo-Fraenkel Set Theory in Computational Complexity."
- [12] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Proof of Millennium Theorem" P versus NP."
- [13] Kyritsis, Konstantinos E. "Study on the Solution of the Clay Millennium Problem about the P vs NP: A Short Proof that $P \neq NP = EXPTIME$ in the Context of Deterministic Turing Machines."
- [14] Anand, Bhupinder Singh. "Does Resolving PvNP Require a Paradigm Shift?" Arxiv preprint arXiv:1003.5602 (2010): n. pag. Print.
- [15] Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Hamiltonian Path Principle on Integral Circuits."
- [16] Yen, Jin Y. "An algorithm for finding shortest routes from all source nodes to a given destination in general networks." Quarterly of applied mathematics 27.4 (1970): 526-530.
- [17] Louiz, Akram. "A Proof That the Set of NP-problems is Bigger Than the Set of P-problems by Using a Logical Consideration." WSEAS Transactions on Computers 22 (2023): 159-170.
- [18] Dobbins, Michael Gene, et al. "Completeness for the complexity class $\forall \exists R$ and area-universality." Discrete & Computational Geometry 70.1 (2023): 154-188.